

Commentary on Integrating Objects of Maharashtra Public Universities Act- 2016, in Academic Libraries in Maharashtra.

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Abstract:

In the context of the evolving landscape of higher education and global competence, the draft of the Maharashtra Public Universities Act-2011 highlighted and proposed positive changes in academic libraries in Maharashtra to prepare youth for global competence. In 2016, the Maharashtra state assembly enacted the final draft of the act, which brought all 11 non-agricultural public universities in Maharashtra and their affiliated colleges under its jurisdiction. The Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016, outlines the fundamental eighteen objectives in Chapter II, aiming to enhance the quality of higher education in the state. These objectives also serve as guiding principles for academic libraries in the state, which are governed by the act. The article systematically explores the key values that are often overlooked when adopting positive changes aligned with these objectives in academic libraries.

Keywords: The Draft of Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2011, the Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016, and the Objectives of the University. Transition in Academic Libraries, Challenges Faced by Academic Libraries, and Core Values for Libraries.

Introduction:

Maharashtra has an extensive and rich history of higher education, with both conventional and modern influences. The state hosts a variety of universities, including public, private, and dedicated institutions. University acts have played a crucial role in shaping the governance and regulation of the higher education sector in Maharashtra. To bring about fundamental change in higher education within the state, the Maharashtra government established various committees, such as the Agrawal committee, Nigavekar committee, Takwale committee, and Kakodkar committee. Considering the recommendations made by these committees, the new Public Universities Act was enacted in 2016. Building on the previous Act of 1994, this legislation introduced new essential reforms. Pioneering the eighteen objects of the university acts as a guiding principle for academic libraries, and implementing these objects will revolutionise the entire landscape of academic libraries in Maharashtra. Although primarily designed for universities, these objects are significantly helpful in bringing about substantial changes in the academic working system and reshaping academic libraries to align with the evolving nature of higher education on a global platform. Fiels (2013) identified the need for change in academic libraries, arguing that “The traditional library was an inactive provider of information, reacting to community information needs, but today the library must be proactive and it must engage its community” (p. 6). The Maharashtra Public Universities Act 2016 explicitly incorporated these objectives, focusing on “disseminate, create and preserve knowledge and understanding by teaching, research and development, skill development, training and education, extension and service and by effective demonstration and

influence of its corporate life on society in general”. The specific objectives are outlined in the table below, illustrating their role in reshaping academic libraries for the new epoch.

The Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016 (MPUA-2016) represents a significant reform in the governance and operation of higher education institutions within the state. Its primary objective is to transform universities into dynamic centres of learning, innovation, and societal engagement. In this context, university libraries—referred to as Knowledge Resource Centres (KRCs)—are envisioned to play a pivotal role. Incorporating the objectives of the Act into academic libraries presents both challenges and opportunities, necessitating their evolution from traditional repositories of books to dynamic hubs of knowledge.

Sr. No	Objects of the University	Guiding value for Libraries
1	Carry out its responsibility of creation, preservation and dissemination of Knowledge.	Knowledge Creation and Knowledge Transfer.
2	Promote discipline and the spirit of intellectual inquiry, and dedicate itself as a fearless academic community to the sustained pursuit of excellence.	Promotion of Research.
3	Encourage individuality and diversity within a climate of tolerance and mutual understanding.	Fulfilling the diversified user needs.
4	promote freedom, secularism, equality, and social justice as enshrined in the Constitution of India, and to be a catalyst in patriotic socio-economic transformation by promoting basic attitudes and values of essence to national development;	Value sensitisation among the users
5	Promote a conducive environment for ensuring social harmony, coexistence, integral humanism and upliftment of the poorest of the poor;	Creating a Learning Ambience at Libraries
6	Extend the benefits of knowledge and skills for the development of individuals and society by associating the university closely with local, regional and national problems of development;	Reaching the end users.
7	Carry out social responsibility as an informed and objective critic, to identify and cultivate talent, to train the right kind of leadership in all walks of life and to help the younger generation to develop proper attitudes, interests and values;	Proper User Orientation

8	Promote equitable distribution of teaching, learning, training and other support services facilities of higher education.	Equitable Access
9	Provide for efficient and responsive administration, scientific and technology management, and develop the organisation of teaching, learning, training, research, and extension.	Competent leadership is required to lead teaching and learning activities.
10	Devise motivational systems to ensure that individual cognitive abilities are not constrained, but rather the innovative spirit and desire to make an actual contribution and realise self-achievement are nurtured.	User-centric services and SDI
11	Promote the acquisition of knowledge in a rapidly developing and changing society and to continually offer opportunities for upgrading knowledge, training and skills in the context of innovations, research and discovery in all fields of human endeavour by developing a higher educational network with the use of modern communication media, information and communication technology and other emerging and future technologies appropriate for a learning society.	Integration of ICT in the working system and collection development.
12	Promote national integration and fraternity, preserve cultural heritage, and inculcate respect for the diverse religions and cultures of India through the study of various religions, literature, history, science, art, civilisations, and cultures.	Instilling human values through cultural heritage.
13	Develop a work culture and promote the dignity of labour through applied components in the syllabi.	Promotion of work culture.
14	Build up financial self-sufficiency by undertaking academic teaching, training, and allied programmes, research and development activities for public and private industries, Governmental organisations at local, regional, national, and global levels, and resource-generative services cost-effectively.	Initiative for Resource Generation.
15	Promote better interaction and coordination among different university institutions and colleges within the university, as well as with other universities in the State, region, nation, and globally, through all available means to enhance the	Promotes Linkages for Knowledge Sharing

	governance of the university and its higher education facilities.	
16	Generate and promote a sense of self-respect and dignity amongst the weaker sections of society.	Staff Training and continuous improvement.
17	To promote gender equality and sensitivity in society.	Open access to knowledge
18	Strive to promote competitive merit and excellence as the sole guiding criterion in all academic and other matters relating to students.	Quality Assurance in Services

Objects of the Act Applicable to Libraries- Short Description:

The MPUA-2016 highlights several key objectives that directly or indirectly influence university libraries as follows;

1. Advancing quality and excellence in higher education and research.
2. Transforming libraries into Knowledge Resource Centres to ensure effortless access to knowledge.
3. Utilising ICT, digitisation, and e-resources to create globally connected universities.
4. Skill development, innovation, and entrepreneurship support through knowledge access.
5. Equity and inclusivity in education, ensuring resources are accessible to all.
6. Enhancing relationships with industry and society through research and extension activities.
7. Transparency and accountability in university governance, including resource allocation.

Incorporating the Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016, Objects in Academic Libraries:

1. University Library's transformation into Knowledge Resource Centre (KRC)

Under the Act, libraries are regarded as Knowledge Resource Centres, where they actively promote knowledge creation and sharing, rather than merely holding books. Libraries must provide:

- Access to print and digital collections.
- Repositories for institutional research outputs.
- Spaces for collaborative learning and innovation.

2. Integration of ICT-Enabled Services.

The mandate of the Act aligns with digitisation, automation, and e-resources integration. Academic libraries must strengthen:

- € Institutional repositories and digital archives.
- € Remote access to databases, journals, and e-books.
- € Library management systems integrated with university ERP platforms.

3. Promotion of Research and Innovation.

Libraries must become knowledge enablers for research and incubation activities by:

- € Offering data support, bibliometric services, and plagiarism detection tools.
- € Creating research commons and innovation labs.
- € Assisting in patent searches, intellectual property awareness, and industry-oriented resources.

4. Confirming Impartiality and Inclusivity

In line with the Act, academic libraries should work towards:

- € Developing resources in regional languages alongside English.
- € Offering inclusive services for differently-abled students.
- € Strengthening outreach to rural and socio-economically disadvantaged learners.

5. Establishment Linkages for Knowledge Sharing.

Libraries can contribute by:

- € Hosting community engagement programs, exhibitions, and public lectures.
- € Curating knowledge resources that address local and regional issues, particularly those relevant to Maharashtra's development.
- € Supporting lifelong learning and extension activities.

6. Governance policy, Transparency, and Accountability.

The Act calls for accountable governance. Libraries must:

- € Adopt transparent acquisition policies.
- € Encourage open access initiatives.
- € Regularly evaluate services through user feedback and quality benchmarks.

Action to be taken:

To ensure effective integration of the Act's objectives within academic libraries:

- € Capacity building of library staff through ICT and research training is essential.
- € Collaborative networks among university libraries in Maharashtra should be strengthened for resource sharing.
- € Policy-level support for adequate funding and modernisation of KRCs is needed.
- € User-centric innovations such as mobile library services, digital literacy programs, and AI-enabled search tools should be encouraged.

Discussion:

The Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016, emphasises the expected shift of Maharashtra's higher education system towards attaining excellence, which is why these objectives have been forwarded to achieve success in that direction. These objects have carried forward the valuable guidelines which match the academic library's conception of the development process. The draft of the Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2011, also explains the vision for providing higher education in Maharashtra state, given the subtitle as "Pathway for transforming higher education into a socio-economic development force".³

The traditional image of academic libraries is gradually transforming, and they are currently in a transitional phase, adapting to changes in their operational systems, user services, staff training, collection development, and technological integration. However, the process of these changes is not without difficulties, as academic libraries face various challenges. The data gathered through the questionnaire, designed to collect the Knowledge Resource Centre in public universities in Maharashtra, revealed the director's views about the challenges facing the Knowledge Resource Centre, as listed below;

- Infrastructural and Digital Concerns
- Financial Constraint
- Recruitment-Related Concerns
- Policy Related Concerns
- Human Resource Development Linked Issues
- Governance And Planning Associated Issues
- Traditional Mindset

Conclusion:

Academic libraries face challenges in fulfilling the key definitions and objectives set by the Maharashtra Public Universities Act, 2016. Despite issues with the expected transition in the overall system of academic libraries, there are glimmers of hope for progress in the coming days, as the Indian government has envisioned the mission India@2047 for a developed nation, accompanied by significant changes in higher education.

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